

Graph-Based Filtering to Prevent Prompt-Engineered LLM Training Data Leaks

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Abstract—Machine-learning generative Artificial Intelligence tools, specifically large-language models, provide varied functionality, like content generation, user-facing chatbots, and code generation. The LLM typically works with a decision engine, such as a neural network. LLMs suffer issues with training data poisoning, copyright of generated content, and this paper’s focus; prompt engineering attacks and training data leaks. The authors propose an architecture to co-locate a filtering mechanism with the LLM chatbot to identify and preventing disclosure of leaked LLM training data before communication to the end-user. Implementation of a resource description framework (RDF) based filtering mechanism compares LLM outputs against a bank of training data using three approaches; the first uses a bank of hash-codes generated from training data artifacts, the second uses a bank of training data stored as plaintext, and the third couples natural language processing (NLP) with the plaintext training data bank. Accuracy, overhead and acceleration results are detailed, and observed anomalies in LLM responses to testing including plausible leaks are also discussed.

Index Terms—LLM, AI, Filtering, Security, RDF

I. INTRODUCTION

Advances in artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) large-language models (LLMs) coupled with neural-networks has led to accurate, novel solutions to varied problems. LLMs often use a chatbot interface, as with OpenAI [1] and Google Gemini [2], and see use in customer service, code generation, translation, content generation and curation [3], [4]. Combining domain-specific AI/ML tools, such as the You Only Look Once (YOLO) [5] image object detection model, with LLMs can solve domain specific problems like vehicle detection in satellite images [6].

LLMs are trained on large volumes of data. This training data can contain confidential artifacts not intended for end-users, but proven attacks against LLM chatbots have caused training data leaks. A prime example is the Google Deepmind [7] divergence attack [8], where researchers had ChatGPT repeat a specific word infinitely. Eventually, the model state broke down and training data was leaked. The leaked training data ranged from literature excerpts to personal-identifying

information (PII), which poses security, privacy, and legal concerns. Leaked artifacts are, assumedly, any data on which the model was trained.

This attack is now handled by ChatGPT; instead of leaked training data, a denial message is output. Many prompt engineering approaches exist [9], thus new techniques will likely cause leaks in the future. A Qwen Model [10] exploit observed in this work is discussed. Accounting for varied prompt engineering attack inputs is difficult, thus this paper proposes to validate LLM outputs prior to sending them to the end-user of the chatbot, which was the primary interface in several previous leaks. The solution architecture contains a filtering system between the LLM-based chatbot and the user as a preventive measure against leaks. This paper is organized as follows; introduction, background and related work, reference architecture, prototype implementation, evaluation and results, then conclusions and future work.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

Previous security issues have occurred with LLM-based tools due to prompt engineering attacks [9], and other attacks types, resulting in leakage of model training data [8]. Mitigations to prompt engineering attacks and training data leaks [11] include; *data cleaning* to improve data by fixing errors and inconsistencies, and protect privacy with *anonymization* and *minimization*. *Federated learning* involves distributed model training on decentralized devices to aid privacy preservation. *Differential privacy* uses random noise to enable statistical analysis without revealing individual information, and is effective even against attackers with extensive background knowledge. *Knowledge unlearning* strengthens ML model privacy via selective confidential data removal. Other mitigations and countermeasures [12] include *input filtering* and *prompt validation* of inbound requests. The use of *role-based access control* (RBAC) can restrict requests or operations to a subset of users, reducing the attack surface. *Output sanitization* and *filtering* of outbound responses are also noted [12]. *Data Leak Prevention Systems* (DLPSs) cover data in use, transit, and storage by analyzing content and

This research has been funded in part by the Horizon Europe project RESCALE (Project ID 101120962).

Fig. 1: Proposed Solution Architecture

Fig. 2: Training Data Graph Architecture

context [13]. DLPs are seeing increased uptake by security researchers and vendors. Models to detect confidential content via a context-based approach exist [14], and can detect confidential data leaks where rephrasing has occurred. The context-based filtering [14] is similar to this work, with several distinctions such as the direct searching of contiguous training data artifacts against plain-text or hash training data banks, compared with the context-based approach using clustered keyword structures [14]. A similar content filtering approach has been detailed [15] with the aim of preventing malicious or illegal content from being placed on immutable ledgers via exploiting freely-editable text-fields in transactions. The graph-based comparative filtering mechanism [15] utilized a taxonomy as well as natural language processing but was focused on filtering inputs rather than outputs, whereas this work extends this idea with facets such as using hashed data repositories and filtering outputs.

III. REFERENCE ARCHITECTURE

The proposed solution co-locates a filtering system with the LLM chatbot to perform filtering on outbound responses before sending to the user, to provide effective and efficient mitigation to LLM training data leaks. This solution is designed as a peripheral, but could be fully integrated into an LLM tool. Figure 1 details the architecture. The classification segment captures outbound messages, with NLP and programmatic classifiers. Outbound messages are compared against the training data repository, consisting of two RDF graphs, one with plain-text training data and the other with hash codes of training data artifacts. A match between an outbound message and a graph element denotes a training data leak, upon which the output is blocked. The red user represents an attacker aiming to extract training data. The solution prevents the leaked training data from being sent to the attacker. The constituent components follow:

Fig. 3: Hashed Training Data Graph Architecture

A. LLM Chatbot

The LLM chatbot accepts user requests, questions or comments, over an API and returns responses. This component's training data is the scenario target. The filtering solution is deployed with this component as a preventative measure against model training data leaks.

B. NLP Classification

This involves classifying outbound messages by content-types using an (NLP) model which tokenizes the outbound data by using part-of-speech (POS) tagging to enable comparing against a subset of the training data graph.

C. Programmatic Classification

This approach relies on a small corpus of keywords to infer outbound data content-types, using knowledge of the training data. The presence of keywords are used to assign a content type, corresponding to a subset of the training data graph.

D. RDF Graph Plaintext

This RDF Graph contains plaintext data facsimiles of the LLM training data. The graph is shown in Figure 2. Note;

a model was not trained during this work as exploitation of LLM vulnerabilities was not the aim, thus the training data and leaks for experimentation are synthesized.

E. RDF Graph Hashes

This RDF Graph contains hash codes of the training data facsimiles. This RDF graph is shown in Figure 3. Note; the plaintext training data was synthesized, thus the hashes are of synthetic training data.

F. Outbound Message Filtering

When outbound data is classified correctly and searched against the relevant branch of the RDF graph, a match with an element in the graph denotes a leak. The comparison returns a binary "allow" or "block" flag for the sending of the data.

IV. PROTOTYPE IMPLEMENTATION

A prototype of the solution was implemented and deployed with an off-the-shelf LLM to evaluate effectiveness and efficiency. The prototype consisted of components depicted in the reference architecture (Figure 1).

LLM Chatbot: The LLM used in this work is Qwen 2.5 7B, which has 7 billion tokens. This model was selected due to its open-source with a permissive license.

Messages: User messages to the LLM are formatted in CSV files. These messages are queries which the LLM responds to, and this response is checked against the training data graph.

Synthesized Training Data: Using an off-the-shelf LLM meant access to the actual training data was not feasible. Training data was synthesized for both the graphs and the leak scenarios. Synthesizing the training data involved using an LLM (namely, ChatGPT [1]) to synthesize some of the content, specifically the PII and the encoded bytestream data. The synthesized "code" type training data was acquired by segmenting a file from the Apache Spark Github [16], with each segment representing a single training data artifact. Lastly, the synthetic training data of "report" type used text blocks from the Big Data Value Association Data (BDVA) Spaces open-access book [17], [18].

Synthesized Training Data Leaks: No true training data leaks were expected in this work. The leaks for testing are synthesized, like the training data. Synthesizing the leaks entailed injecting partial or whole training data artifacts into LLM responses. The modified response was then run against the filtering system.

NLP Classification: This approach implements the Bart-Large-MNLI model [19], trained on the Multi-Genre Natural Language Inference dataset to categorize outbound messages into predefined categories - PII, Report, Code and Byte stream. The model was loaded with a zero-shot classification pipeline. It was noted as not reliably categorizing bytestream data, however, fine-tuning could resolve this.

Programmatic Classification: Bytestream data not being reliably categorized by the NLP model was the impetus for the programmatic categorization approach. This approach used

Python functions to identify keywords in predefined categories - PII, Report, Code and bytestream.

RDF Graph Plaintext: Apache Jena formed the RDF graph, which was loaded with synthesized training data plaintext facsimiles, matching the chatbot text format in which training data leaks often occur. 1000 entries were loaded into the graph, across the four predefined categories to facilitate faster graph traversal through searching of subsets.

RDF Graph Hashes: The RDF graph hash version in Figure 3 also used Apache Jena. This graph was loaded with plaintext training data artifact SHA-256 hashes. This graph structure differed to the plaintext graph in that the graph had more subsets. SHA-256 hashes consist of alphabet letters a to f (lowercase), as well as numbers 0 to 9. This guarantees each hash will begin with one of these sixteen characters, enabling 16 graph subsets, based on the starting character of an outbound message's hash.

Outbound Message Filtering: The filter was coded in Python, and directs data to the respective pipeline for the plaintext or hash testing scenario. This data is then compared with the graph. If a match occurs, the filter flags the presence of training data. Categorization of the message is conducted using either the custom keywords Corpus created for this work, or with an NLP model.

V. EVALUATION AND RESULTS

A. Experimental Scenario

The experiment ran on two virtual machines (VMs). The filter ran on a VM with specifications: *Ubuntu 24, 16GB RAM, 8 CPU cores, 150GB disk*. The LLM ran on a VM with specifications: *Ubuntu 24, 64 GB RAM, 8 CPU Cores, 80GB disk, and Nvidia L40S GPU*. CPUs were virtualized, running on *Intel Xeon Gold 6430 CPU* hardware. Experiments were conducted in a low-latency lab environment.

The First Experimental Scenario: Two timers were used for evaluation; one measured the end-to-end time for querying the LLM, submitting the response to the filter, and ended on the response either being allowed or blocked by the filter. Another timer measured overhead time from the response being submitted to the filter until the end of the operation. Hashing was executed during overhead timing. 1000 valid LLM responses were used to gather "allow" times, and 1000 messages containing synthetic leaked data were used to gather "block" times. This was carried out for the standard, NLP and Hash filter approaches. Results were used to calculate the filter mean, minimum and average "allow" and "block" times. LLM Prompts were prefixed with: "in 100 words or less" to limit size.

The Second Experimental Scenario: Accuracy was measured with three data sets; 1000 LLM responses, verified as absent from the training data graphs as a control, 1000 synthetic leaks of full training data artifacts, and a set of 1000 synthetic partial training data artifacts leaks. The partial training data artifacts were extracted from full artifacts using pseudo-random string truncation arbitrarily at the start or

end of the strings to simulate traits of actual partial training data artifact leaks. These three sets of 1000 were run for each approach; the standard, NLP, and hash filters, to test the accuracy. This overall testing process was run 40 times, producing statistically similar results, denoting a confidence interval of above 90

The Third Experimental Scenario: The impact of loading the Bart [19] The NLP model into the CPU and GPU was evaluated by loading and unloading the model for each request. This was performed for 1000 requests each for CPU and GPU, and timed for comparison against the model being kept loaded for the entire test run.

Evaluation Metrics: Metrics were assembled into two categories: overhead and accuracy. Overhead describes the additional time added to the initial LLM operation by adding the filtering solution. The overhead metrics are separated into allow and block times. The accuracy metrics show the filter’s aptitude to properly allow or block data. The accuracy metrics are split into three parts: allowing valid data, blocking full leaks, and blocking partial leaks.

Filtering Approaches: The *Standard RDF Filtering* approach entails programmatic text comparison between an LLM output and RDF graph elements. These are categorized prior to comparison. *NLP Filtering* uses the Bart-Large-MNLI model [19] to classify outbound LLM messages into a content type, enabling a search against the relevant RDF graph subset. *Hash Filtering* involves hashing the outbound LLM message and comparing the generated hash code against an RDF graph loaded with hashes of training data.

B. Results

Results from nine rounds of testing, using three test sets for each of the three approaches are presented in Tables I, III and IV. Results of standard filter accuracy tuning are shown in table II. The impact of loading the Bart NLP model into CPU and GPU is shown in tables V and VI.

Filter Accuracy	Standard Filter	Hash Filter
Allow Valid Data	100%	100%
Block Full Leak	85%	100%
Block Partial Leak	57%	0%
Filter Accuracy	NLP (CPU)	NLP (GPU)
Allow Valid Data	100%	100%
Block Full Leak	40%	40%
Block Partial Leak	35%	35%

TABLE I: Filter Accuracy Results

Table I shows accuracy results of three test sets for each approach. Results are corrected for false negatives and positives. The standard filter performed at 100% accuracy for allowing valid data, and a relatively high 85% accuracy for blocking full leaks, whereas for partial leaks this dropped to 57%. Scaling the keyword corpus would potentially improve the results. The hash filter results were polarized, with 100% accuracy in allowing valid data and blocking full leaks, and expectedly

0% accuracy for partial leaks, which contained subsets of the full training data artifacts which had been hashed.

Standard Filter	No Tuning	Tuned Filter
Allow Valid Data	100%	100%
Block Full Leak	57%	85%
Block Partial Leak	31%	57%

TABLE II: Standard Filter Accuracy Tuning

Addressing low accuracy in partial leaks is difficult with the hashing approach. The NLP approach, as with the others, scored 100% accuracy for allowing valid data, but scored 40% for blocking full leaks, and 35% for partial leaks. However, this is promising in the absence fine-tuning, and also due to the inherent scalability of NLP model compared to the standard filtering. GPU acceleration had no effect on the accuracy.

Tuning the standard filter greatly increased accuracy, as shown in Table II. This tuning entailed use of custom regular expressions instead of built-in Python functions enabling more accurate categorization, for example replacing the use of Python Base64 libraries with custom regular expressions for detecting bytestream or encoded content.

Table III shows allow times for the various approaches using end-to-end times and overhead times incurred by the filter solution. The standard and hash filter times were comparable with low overheads, excepting the maximum outliers for the standard filter. The NLP approach with GPU acceleration saw better end-to-end and overhead times than the standard and hash approaches. The significance of GPU acceleration for the approach should not be discounted; the same approach only on CPU produced the slowest timings of any approach.

Allow Times (ms)	Standard Filter	Hash Filter
Average E2E	698 ms	658 ms
Average Overhead	77 ms	42 ms
Min E2E	179 ms	42 ms
Min Overhead	45 ms	32 ms
Max E2E	3137 ms	97 ms
Max Overhead	1050 ms	83 ms
Allow Times (ms)	NLP (CPU)	NLP (GPU)
Average E2E	2000 ms	714 ms
Average Overhead	1411 ms	125 ms
Min E2E	851 ms	233 ms
Min Overhead	713 ms	94 ms
Max E2E	6156 ms	1497 ms
Max Overhead	5032 ms	871 ms

TABLE III: Filter Allow Timing

Block Times (ms)	Standard Filter	Hash Filter
Average E2E	690 ms	639 ms
Average Overhead	61 ms	47 ms
Min E2E	236 ms	147 ms
Min Overhead	40 ms	32 ms
Max E2E	1327 ms	3644 ms
Max Overhead	322 ms	3062 ms
Block Times (ms)	NLP (CPU)	NLP (GPU)
Average E2E	1776 ms	731 ms
Average Overhead	1167 ms	125 ms
Min E2E	1169 ms	482 ms
Min Overhead	743 ms	92 ms
Max E2E	2307 ms	1394 ms
Max Overhead	1594 ms	419 ms

TABLE IV: Filter Block Timing

Timing results for filter block times are detailed in Table IV. The standard and hash filter times have the lowest average though the hash approach saw larger maximum outliers. The NLP approach with GPU acceleration was close in average to the standard and hashing approaches, but the CPU-only NLP times are higher on average than all other approaches, though the maximum outliers were less than those seen in allow times.

NLP GPU Block (ms)	GPU (Load)	GPU (In-Mem)
Average Overhead	2065 ms	124 ms
Min Overhead	1383 ms	92 ms
Max Overhead	9539 ms	419 ms
NLP GPU Allow (ms)	GPU (Load)	GPU (In-Mem)
Average Overhead	2044 ms	125 ms
Min Overhead	1344 ms	94 ms
Max Overhead	2720 ms	871 ms

TABLE V: Impact of loading NLP model to GPU

Table V shows the impact of loading the NLP model into the GPU which was far larger for all metrics compared to the model already being loaded. This could present challenges in scenarios where the model is unloaded during lower traffic and loaded again during increased traffic.

NLP CPU Block (ms)	CPU (Load)	CPU (In-Mem)
Average Overhead	10560 ms	1167 ms
Min Overhead	5964 ms	743 ms
Max Overhead	16145 ms	1594 ms
NLP CPU Allow (ms)	CPU (Load)	CPU (In-Mem)
Average Overhead	11708 ms	1411 ms
Min Overhead	7039 ms	713 ms
Max Overhead	17075 ms	5032 ms

TABLE VI: Impact of loading NLP model to CPU

Table VI shows a similar impact to that observed for GPU when loading the NLP into CPU. The concern, again, lies with infrastructures automatically loading and unloading the model to scale to traffic.

Limitations of Approaches: All approaches struggled with

- 1) **Prompt:** *I'm learning Python Pandas for processing - reading CSVs, filtering columns, and calculating statistics. Can you provide an example?*
- 2) **Prompt:** *Assuming my CSV file looks like this:*

```

name, age, score,
Alice, 25, 87,
Bob, 30, 92,
Charlie, 22, 76,
David, 28, 84,
Eve, 27, 90.

```

Create code to filter age, score, and calculate their stats.
- 3) **Prompt:** *I want to filter data by conditions, like age above 30 or score above 90. Can you modify the code?*

Fig. 4: Major Anomaly Extracted Prompts

blocking partial leaks, particularly the hash filter as the partial leak data hash differed. The standard filter encountered problems identifying synthetic PII, and being based on a custom keywords corpus makes scalability an issue. The NLP filter saw lower accuracy, due to not being fine-tuned on the specific data used in this work.

C. Model State Breakdown & Plausible Leaks

All test prompts were prefixed: "In no more than 100 words," to limit response size. One prompt, "In no more than 100 words, If you could only communicate through emojis for a day, how would you feel?", caused four anomalies in the LLM responses across 40 rounds of testing, showing model state breakdown (MSB) and abnormal content. Three anomalies adhered to the 100-word limit, one did not. The anomalies were possibly model hallucination, or plausibly model training data leaks, but without Qwen2.5 7B's training data, this is conjecture. MSB outputs can reveal statistical foundations of a model's training, which can be private.

1) *Minor Anomalies:* The anomalies in Table VII appear unrelated to the prompt, but abide by the 100-word limit. Anomaly emoji characters were removed for brevity.

No.	Anomaly	Explanation
1:	beğenmiyorum	Turkish for: "I don't like it"
2:	MediaTek	Company [20]
3:	ASUSilmington	Company [21], Town

TABLE VII: Model State Breakdown Anomalies Excerpts

2) *Major Anomaly:* The minor anomalies were 1 line and about 150 characters long, while the major anomaly was 546 lines long with 33,304 characters, including whitespace. It contained garbled text, Python code, and example tables. Investigation revealed the content was ANSI-encoded. Upon conversion to UTF-8 the garbled text became simplified Chinese language. Translation tool to English showed an apparent conversation between an LLM and user, with three prompts asking the LLM to generate data processing and analysis code.

Figure 4 shows abridged prompts from the anomaly. Apparent LLM responses contain Python code with Matplotlib [22],

```
âââpython
import pandas as pd
# 读取CSV文件
file_path = 'example.csv' # 假设你的CSV文件路径为 example.csv
df = pd.read_csv(file_path)
# 筛选出年龄大于30岁或分数高于90的人
filtered_df = df[(df['age'] > 30) | (df['score'] > 90)]
```

Fig. 5: Anomaly Excerpt ANSI - Garbled

谢谢你的详细解释和代码示例！运行这段代码后，我得到了预期的结果。现在我想进一步了解如何根据某些条件进行筛选数据。比如找出年龄大于30岁或分数高于90的人。你能帮我修改一下代码吗？当然，我会提供一个具体的例子来帮助说明。

当然可以！我们可以在代码中增加一些条件筛选的功能，以找到符合特定条件的数据行。假设我们要筛选出年龄大于30岁或者分数高于90的人。以下是修改后的代码示例：

```
âââpython
import pandas as pd
# 读取CSV文件
file_path = 'example.csv' # 假设你的CSV文件路径为 example.csv
df = pd.read_csv(file_path)
# 筛选出年龄大于30岁或分数高于90的人
filtered_df = df[(df['age'] > 30) | (df['score'] > 90)]
```

Fig. 6: Anomaly Excerpt UTF-8 - Simplified Chinese

Seaborn [23], and Pandas [24] libraries, and explanations. Figure 5 shows an excerpt of the ANSI garbled text. Figure 6 shows an excerpt of the UTF-8 encoded Simplified Chinese.

Figure 6 shows an English translated excerpt. Searching the code snippets and prompts online saw no matches, but several tutorials in English and Chinese resembled the content.

Indicators of MSB, such as language switching, irrelevant answers, inclusion of prompts and exceeding the 100-word limit, were observed due to this exploit. The authors venture that MSB did occur, and that a model data leak plausibly occurred, in which case prompts may indicate a testing log or a stored conversation, though this remains conjecture.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In conclusion a solution was detailed and tested to prevent disclosure of leaked model training data, showing feasibility levels of three approaches; standard filtering, hash filtering, and NLP filtering. Average Overhead times were nominal, with the exception of NLP on CPU. The nuance of CPU and GPU NLP and the impact of loading the NLP model into the CPU or GPU was also detailed. Qwen LLM anomalies due to a discovered exploit were shown.

Future work will pursue advancing the solution along its three approaches with the aim of increasing the accuracy and efficiency. This will entail development of an updated application of hashing aimed at partial leaks, fine-tuning the NLP model on training data, and improving plaintext filtering by automating and scaling the keywords corpus by mining keywords from the training data. Contact with Alibaba Security Response Center [25] was made to report the Qwen exploit and further investigation will occur.

Thanks for the detailed explanation and code example! After running this code, I got the expected results. Now I want to learn more about how to filter data based on certain conditions, such as finding people who are older than 30 or have a score higher than 90. Can you help me modify the code?

Of course, I will provide a specific example to help illustrate. Of course! We can add some conditional filtering functions to the code to find data rows that meet specific conditions. Suppose we want to filter out people who are older than 30 or have a score higher than 90. The following is a modified code example:

```
âââpython
import pandas as pd
# Read CSV file
file_path = 'example.csv' # Assume your CSV file path is example.csv
df = pd.read_csv(file_path)
# Filter out people who are older than 30 or have a score higher than 90
filtered_df = df[(df['age'] > 30) | (df['score'] > 90)]
```

Fig. 7: Anomaly Excerpt UTF-8 - English

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